

STUDIES IN THE NEGATIVELY CHARGED COLLOIDAL SOLUTIONS OF VARIOUS FERRIC SALTS. PART II. NEGATIVELY CHARGED FERRIC BORATE SOL

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The conditions of preparation of negatively charged ferric borate sol have been studied. The method principally consists in adding sodium borate solution to ferric chloride solution and dispersing the precipitate of ferric borate by caustic soda in presence of glucose or glycerine. The composition of the sol peptised in presence of glucose appears to be $11\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{FeBO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and of that peptised in presence of glycerine is probably $5\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{FeBO}_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Prakash and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 391) reported that when a saturated solution of borax was added gradually to ferric chloride solution, a bulky precipitate appeared which dissolved on shaking. After dialysis, a clear red sol was obtained which set to form transparent jellies on addition of KCl or K_2SO_4 . Prakash and Dhar (*ibid.*, p. 587) also reported the formation of stannic borate jellies obtained by coagulating stannic borate sols. Mitra (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1939, 9, 138) studied the periodic precipitation of ferric borate sol by the process of coagulation with electrolytes. The sols and gels investigated so far are charged positively. No work appears to have been done on the negatively charged ferric borate sols.

In a previous publication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 111), we have made attempts to study the negatively charged sols of ferric vanadate and in this paper our results on the negatively charged ferric borate sols are reported.

When borax is added to ferric chloride solution, a voluminous yellow precipitate of ferric borate is obtained. We have observed that this precipitate of ferric borate can be dispersed by caustic soda in presence of glucose or glycerine to give a bright red sol of ferric borate which bears a negative charge. Mushran and Prakash (*Allahabad Univ. Studies*, 1943, 19, 1) have studied the detailed conditions of the preparation of this sol. The idea of peptisation can be had from the following figures.

1.0 to 2.0 c.c. of a ferric chloride solution (30.36 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre) when mixed with 1.0 to 1.6 c.c. of 8% borax solution in presence of 0.6 to 1.0 c.c. of 20% glucose solution requires 3.0 to 4.6 c.c. of $N/3$ -NaOH solution (total volume 10 c.c.) to bring about complete peptisation in half an hour.

1.0 to 2.0 c.c. of the same ferric chloride solution when mixed with 1.0 to 2.0 c.c. of 8% borax solution in presence of 0.5 to 3.0 c.c. of glycerine requires 3.0 to 4.8 c.c. of $N/3$ -NaOH (total volume 10 c.c.) to bring about the complete peptisation in half an hour.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sol A was prepared by mixing 60 c.c. of a ferric chloride solution (30.36 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre), 180 c.c. of 8% borax solution, 174 c.c. of 20% glucose solution and 200 c.c. of N -NaOH solution. The sol was purified by dialysis for a period of 10 days and was found quite stable.

Sol B was prepared by mixing 50 c.c. of the same ferric chloride solution, 240 c.c. of 8% borax solution, 120 c.c. of glycerine and 160 c.c. of N -NaOH solution. The sol was subjected to cold dialysis for purification. It was observed that the sol could not stand much dialysis. It was thrown out as a gelatinous mass during dialysis for a day. The sol under investigation was therefore dialysed for about twelve hours and was then

transferred to a Jena bottle. The dialysed sol was unstable and was thrown out in the course of seven days.

The amount of iron in a known volume of the sol was estimated by the use of the reagent cupferron. An analysis is presented in Table I.

TABLE I

Per litre.	Sol A	Sol B
	Glucose sol.	Glycerine sol.
Total iron	1.2952 g.	1.3864 g.
Total borate (H_3BO_3)	0.6200	0.6610
Combined borate (H_3BO_3)	0.1240	0.1421
Free borate (H_3BO_3)	0.4960	0.8189
Combined iron	0.1120	0.1284
Free iron	1.1832	1.2580
Viscosity of sol (30°)	0.00835	0.00892*
Viscosity of water (30°)	0.00803	0.00803
Water, bound	0.05626	0.99310
Empirical formula	$11Fe_2O_3 \cdot 2FeBO_3 \cdot 3H_2O$	$5Fe_2O_3 \cdot FeBO_3 \cdot 24H_2O^*$

* The high viscosities are due to the presence of a sufficient concentration of free glycerine, as the sol could not be dialysed long. The instability of the sol also contributed towards this end

The amount of bound water per litre of the sol was calculated from the Hatschek's equation (*cf. Mushran, Curr. Sci., 1945, 14, 233*).

The sols were coagulated cataphoretically as well as by $N/2$ -KCl, centrifuged, and the p_H values of the supernatant aqueous layers were determined using the Hildebrand's hydrogen electrode. The following p_H values are recorded :

Sol A	7.32 (KCl-coagulated)	7.34 (cataphoretically coagulated)
Sol B	7.56 (KCl-coagulated)	7.60 (cataphoretically coagulated)

Sp. Conductivities of the Sols

The conductivities of the sols at various dilutions, at different temperatures and also on ageing have been investigated. The results are recorded in the following tables.

TABLE II A

Sp. conductivity at different dilutions (30°)

Dilution.	Conductivity $\times 10^4$ mho.		Dilution.	Conductivity $\times 10^4$ mho.	
	Sol A.	Sol B.		Sol A.	Sol B.
Original sol (X)	5.21	57.59	Original sol X/2	2.70	40.39
5X/6	4.36	55.61	X/3	1.87	29.53
2X/3	3.55	51.47	X/6	0.94	17.80

TABLE II B

Sp. conductivity on ageing (30°)

Dates.	Conductivity $\times 10^4$ mho.		Dates.	Conductivity $\times 10^4$ mho.	
	Sol A.	Sol B.		Sol A.	Sol B.
2-11-44	5.11	..	2-2-45	6.00	..
7-11-44	5.21	..	22-2-45	..	57.59
16-11-44	5.41	..	29-2-45	..	The sol settles down
20-12-44	5.67	..	12-3-45	6.08	..

TABLE II C
Sp. conductivity at different temperatures

Temp.	Sol A.		Sol B.	
	Sp. condy. $\times 10^4$ mho.	Diff. per 5°.	Sp. condy. $\times 10^4$ mho.	Diff. per 5°.
40°	6.30		69.98	
35°	5.81	0.49	63.99	5.99
30°	5.23	0.58	57.59	6.40
25°	4.76	0.47	51.19	6.40
20°	4.27	0.49	44.81	6.38
Temp. of zero conductance (extrapolated)		-22.0°		-16.5°
Temp. coefficient per 1°		0.10		1.26

From the above data it appears that sol A is fairly stable on dilution, as the conductivities of this sol are proportional to the dilutions. In the case of sol B, the conductivities are always higher than those computed on the basis of dilution. Marked hydrolysis of the sol B is thus indicated. The conductivities of the sols increase with age. The conductivity-temperature curves are straight lines. The temperatures of zero conductance of the sols range between -16.5° and -22° .

It will be of interest to study the temperature coefficients of the sols. The temperature coefficients and the conductivities at 35° are given below.

	Conductivity at 35° .	Temperature coefficient per 1°.
Sol A	5.81×10^{-4} mho	0.10
Sol B	63.99	1.26

The temperature coefficient of sol A is 1.72% of the conductance at 35° and of sol B is 1.97% of the conductance at 35° . The temperature coefficients are thus always less than 2% of the conductances at 35° .

Extinction Coefficients of the Sols

Extinction coefficients were determined by the Nutting's spectrophotometer at different dilutions and at different wave-lengths (X stands for the original undiluted sol).

TABLE III

Wave-lengths.	Sol A.				Wave-lengths.	Sol B.		
	X.	X/2.	X/4.	X/8.		X.	X/2.	X/4.
4800 Å.	3.80	1.90	0.95	0.48	4800 A	2.92	1.70	0.95
5000	2.70	1.35	0.63	0.32	5000	2.46	1.41	0.81
5200	1.85	0.92	0.46	0.23	5200	2.03	1.15	0.66
5400	1.18	0.60	0.31	0.16	5400	1.61	0.97	0.51
5600	0.85	0.43	0.22	0.11	5600	1.20	0.78	0.41
5800	0.51	0.25	0.13	0.07	5800	0.82	0.50	0.27
6000	0.39	0.20	0.10	0.05	6000	0.55	0.39	0.22
6200	0.25	0.13	0.07	0.04	6200	0.43	0.32	0.19
6400	0.20	0.10	0.06	0.03				

From these data, it will be seen that in the case of sol A Beer's law is almost rigidly followed, i.e., the extinction coefficients are almost proportional to the dilutions. In the case of sol B, the extinction coefficients are always greater than those computed on the basis of dilution. The hydrolysis of ferric borate at different dilutions has caused deviations in the extinction coefficient-dilution relationship. Our results on the conductivities at different dilutions (Table II A) also show similar behaviour.

Coagulation of the Sols

In the following table are recorded the minimum amounts of electrolytes necessary to coagulate 1 c.c. of the sols in a total volume of 10 c.c., the time allowed in each case being 30 minutes.

TABLE IV

Electrolytes.	Amount necessary to coagulate.		Electrolytes.	Amount necessary to coagulate.	
	Sol A.	Sol B.		Sol A.	Sol B.
N/2-NaCl	1.70 c.c.	0.60 c.c.	N/2-KBr	1.50 c.c.	0.40 c.c.
N/2-KCl	1.50	0.40	N/250-Ba(NO ₃) ₂	1.80	0.60
			N/250-Sr(NO ₃) ₂	2.00	0.90
N/2-KNO ₃	1.50	0.40	N/250-AlCl ₃	1.20	0.30

The coagulating power of the ions thus fall in the following series :

The effect of dilution on the coagulation values has also been investigated.

TABLE V

Total vol. = 10 c.c.

Electrolytes.	Vol. necessary to coagulate					
	Sol A			Sol B		
	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.
N/2-NaCl	1.70	1.80	1.90	0.60	0.70	0.80
N/2-KCl	1.50	1.60	1.70	0.40	0.50	0.60
N/2-KNO ₃	1.50	1.60	1.70	0.40	0.50	0.80

From Table V it is evident that the sols obey the Schulze-Hardy rule for the coagulation with electrolytes. They show the normal behaviour with dilution.

Positively Charged Ferric Borate Sols

It has been observed by previous workers (Prakash and Dhar, *loc. cit.*) that ferric chloride solutions dissolve a considerable amount of borax to give a positively charged sol of ferric borate. In Table VI are given our results on the composition of some positively charged ferric borate sols.

Sol A was prepared by mixing 20 c.c. of ferric chloride solution (69.84 g. of Fe₂O₃ per litre), 80 c.c. of 8% borax solution. The total volume was kept 100 c.c. The sol was dialysed for two days.

Sol B was prepared by mixing 20 c.c. of the same ferric chloride solution and 70 c.c. of 8% borax solution. The total volume was kept 90 c.c. The sol was dialysed for two days.

Estimations for iron and borate were made in the same manner as in the case of the negatively charged ferric borate sols.

TABLE VI

Per litre.	Sol A.	Sol B.
Total iron	8.7495 g.	9.0220 g
Combined borate (H ₃ BO ₃)	1.9200	1.7360
Combined iron	1.7360	1.5680
Free iron	7.0135	7.4540
Viscosity of sol	0.00840	0.00838
Water, bound	0.08545	0.07200
Empirical formula	2Fe ₂ O ₃ .FeBO ₃ . 0.2 H ₂ O	5Fe ₂ O ₃ .2FeBO ₃ . 0.3 H ₂ O
Sol A contained 2.3640 g. of chloride ions per litre		
Sol B contained 2.1276 g. of chloride ions per litre		

DISCUSSION

It is difficult to say if the ferric borate precipitated by the reaction between borax and ferric chloride solutions, has a composition corresponding to *ortho*-, *meta*-, or *tetra*-borate. Similar anomalous behaviour occurs in the case of other borate salts precipitated when a borax solution is used. According to Hartley and Ramage, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 129) a bulky precipitate was obtained by adding a solution of manganese sulphate slowly to a solution of borax at 22.4°. This precipitate on washing and drying in *vacuo* furnished a bulky brownish white powder. Analysis of this substance corresponded with the composition of monohydrated manganese tetrahydro-*orthoborate*. The reaction was represented as :

The same compound was produced by treating borax with sodium hydroxide and manganese sulphate :

On the analogy of manganese *orthoborate* salt, thus precipitated, we may presume the precipitation of ferric *orthoborate* when borax is added to ferric chloride solution. At any rate, the negatively charged ferric borate sol is likely to have this composition when it is peptised with caustic alkali. The reaction may be represented as follows :

For the positively charged sol, one can assign either a *metaborate* or a *tetraborate* constitution. In such cases, ferric borate is precipitated according to one of the following equations :

However, for comparison, we have given the composition of positively charged sols also in the form of *orthoborate*. The general composition of ferric borate may be expressed by a formula : $z\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot y\text{B}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot z\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

During the course of dialysis (specially in the presence of alkali) ferric borate is hydrolysed to substances of various compositions showing ultimately the following equilibria :

The orthoboric acid being tribasic, ferric borate may have dihydrogen and monohydrogen compositions also :

These substances also gradually hydrolyse giving ultimately a mixed composition of ferric borate and ferric oxide.

The compositions of various negatively and positively charged ferric borate sols studied in this paper are :

Negatively charged : (i) $11\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{FeBO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (ii) $5\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{FeBO}_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Positively charged : (i) $2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{FeBO}_3 \cdot 0.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (ii) $5\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{FeBO}_3 \cdot 0.3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

From the compositions given here it is clear that the positively charged sols contain proportionately a higher content of ferric borate.

CONCLUSION

We have studied in details the various characteristics of the negatively charged ferric borate sol and from the results recorded in the foregoing tables the following observations may be summarised :

1. The electrical conductivity of the sol, peptised in presence of glucose, is approximately proportional to the dilution, whilst in the case of the sol peptised in presence of glycerine, at no stage is it proportional to the dilution. Marked hydrolysis of the glycerine sol on dilution is thus indicated.
2. The electrical conductivities of both the glucose and the glycerine sols are linear functions of temperatures. The temperatures of zero conductance lie between -16.2° and -22° .
3. The temperature coefficients of conductivity of the sols are always less than 2% of the conductances at 35° .
4. Effect of ageing on the conductivity of the glucose sols shows an increase in conductivity with ageing. The sol peptised in presence of glycerine is very unstable and is thrown out in the course of a week.
5. The changes in the extinction coefficients with dilution show that whilst Beer's law is obeyed in the case of the glucose sol, it is not obeyed in the case of the glycerine sol. The extinction coefficients of the glycerine sol do not decrease with dilution in the same proportion indicating hydrolysis of this sol on dilution.
6. The p_s values of the dispersion medium lie between 7.32 and 7.60 showing that the sols are slightly basic owing to the stabilising hydroxide ions.
7. The sols obey the Schulze-Hardy rule for the coagulation with electrolytes. They show the normal behaviour with dilution.